
**INGLIZ VA RUS TILLARIDA INSONNING EMOTSIONAL HOLATINI
IFODALAYDIGAN FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOKOGNITIV
TAHLILI**

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Annotatsiya.

Ushbu maqola ingliz va rus tillarida ham og'zaki ham yozma nutqda qo'llaniladigan turli frazeologik birliklarning o'zaro qiyosiy lingvokognitiv tahlilini amalga oshiradi. Maqolada insonning emotsional holatini bildiruvchi iboralar tanlab olinib, ularning kelib chiqishi, kognitiv xususiyatlari o'rganiladi. Qiyosiy tahlil esa ikki til emotsional frazeologik birliklari o'rtasidagi turli farq va o'xshashlik tomonlarini aniqlashda ko'maklashadi.

Kalit so'zlar.

konsept, mentalitet, madaniy unsur, xalq og'zaki ijodi, tadqiq etmoq, ifodali, representasiya

Annotation.

This article carries out a comparative linguocognitive analysis of various phraseological units used in both oral and written speech in English and Russian. In the article, the expressions expressing the emotional state of a person are selected, and their origin and cognitive characteristics are studied. Comparative analysis helps to identify the differences and similarities between the emotional phraseological units of the two languages.

Key words.

concept, mentality, cultural element, folklore, research, expressive, representation

Аннотация.

В данной статье проводится сравнительный лингвокогнитивный анализ различных фразеологизмов, употребляемых как в устной, так и в письменной речи на английском и русском языках. В статье выбираются выражения, выражающие эмоциональное состояние человека, исследуются их происхождение и когнитивные характеристики. Сравнительный анализ помогает выявить различия и сходства между эмоциональными фразеологизмами двух языков.

Ключевые слова.

концепт, менталитет, элемент культуры, фольклор, исследование, экспрессивность, репрезентация

Insonning ruhiy holati va his-tuyg'ulari uning nutqi va tashqi ko'rinishi orqali namoyon bo'ladi. Nutqning ta'sirchanligi va emotsionalligini oshirishga xizmat qiladigan so'zlar, shuningdek, frazeologik birliklar o'z ma'nolari bilan inson ruhiyatiga ta'sir etish xususiyatiga ega. Shu boisdan fikrni tinglovchiga yetkazishda frazeologizmlar ham boshqa til birliklari singari voqea-hodisalarni aks ettirishda o'ziga xos ta'sirchanligi bilan ajralib turadi. Ularning asosiy ahamiyati nutqni ifodalashda unga hissiy rang berish va uning ma'nosini mustahkamlashdan iboratdir. Insonlardagi ichki kechinmalarning hissiyot, kayfiyat va hayajon tarzida botiniy shaklda boshdan kechirilishi bilan bir qatorda tashqi ruhiyatda seziladigan darajada zohiriy belgilar ham yuzaga chiqadi. Masalan, qo'l va gavdaning ma'noli harakatlari, yuzning ifodali harakatlari (mimika), ovoz ohangi, ko'z va yuz rangining o'zgarishi, turq-tarovati, ko'z qorachig'ining kengayishi yoki torayishi kabilar shular jumlasidandir. Bunday ruhiy kechinmalarni til orqali ifodalash uchun aksariyat hollarda frazeologik iboralar eng samarali vosita sanaladi. Masalan, frazeologiyada insonning ichki kechinmalarini asosan, uning ovoz ohangi, jismoniy harakati, yuz tuzilishi, ko'z qarashlari va yonoqlar rangi orqali ifodalovchi iboralar dominant birliklar hisoblanadi. Shundan kelib chiqqan holda tilda his-tuyg'uning frazeologik birliklar yordamida ifodalanish holatini umumiy tarzda quyidagicha izohlash mumkin: daxshatdan qichqirmoq; g'azabdan bo'kirmoq; quvonchdan osmonga sakramoq; turgan joyida qotib qolmoq; ko'zlari katta - katta bo'lmoq; ko'zlari quvonchdan porlamoq; hayotga kulib boqmoq; og'zi qulog'ida bo'lmoq; baxtdan huzurlanmoq;

Frazeologik birliklarning emotsionalligi insonning turli xil his-tuyg'ulari, hamda shaxs-predmetlarga nisbatan subyektiv munosabatlarini ifodalash bilan bog'liqdir. Bunday emotsionallik bir vaqtning o'zida ikki ma'noning reallashuvi va obrazlilik natijasida yuzaga chiqadi. Darhaqiqat, rang komponentli FBlar qo'rquv, shodlik, azoblanish, hayrat, g'azab, taajjub, norozilik, uyat, g'am, qayg'u, tushkunlik kabi emotsional xususiyatlarni ifodalash imkoniyatiga ega. Bunday ruhiy hayajon va harakat turlari insonning ichki his-tuyg'ulariga xos holat tarzi bo'lib hisoblanadi.

His-tuyg'ular albatta, ikki qutbli -ijobiy yoki salbiy, ya'ni yoqimli va yoqimsiz bo'ladi [Xaydarov F., Xalilova N.: 232]. Psixologik jihatdan iliq ranglar kishida

kayfichog'lik, sovuq ranglar esa ma'yuslik tuyg'usini uyg'otadi [<https://znano.ru/media/ranglarning-hul-atvorimizga-tasiri-2521690>]. Biroq, bunday qarash frazeologiyada qisman mos kelishi mumkin. Negaki, har bir rang frazeologik birlik tarkibida kelganda, turlicha ma'no kasb etadi. Xususan, ijobiy fazilatlarni ham, shu bilan bir qatorda, salbiy xususiyatlarni ham ifodalashi mumkin. Quyida ular xususida alohida to'xtalib o'tamiz: ruhiyatni tasvirlovchi FBlar tarkibida qo'rquv, sarosima, g'azab kabi ma'nolarni anglatib kelishi mumkin. Masalan: dokadek oqarib ketmoq; murdadek oqarib ketmoq; devordek oqarib ketmoq; qizishib ketmoq. Frazeologik iboralar inson ruhiyatiga aloqador xususiyatlarni ifodalashda, asosan, g'azab, rashk, qo'rquv va sovuqlik kabi tushunchalarni aks ettiradi. Masalan: g'azabi qaynamoq; qattiq rashk qilmoq; qattiq qo'rqib ketmoq; sovuqdan ko'karib ketmoq. g'azab otiga minmoq ; darrov ko'ngliga olmoq (ta'sirlanmoq); joni xalqumiga kelmoq; yo'qotib qo'yimoq (dovdiramoq); o'zini osmonda his qilmoq (kayf-safo qilmoq) kabilar hisoblanib, ular inson ruhiyatiga oid xususiyatlarni ifodalashda, asosan, ikkiyuzlamachilik va g'azab tushunchalarini ifodalashga xizmat qiladi. Masalan: majburan kulmoq; iljaymoq; g'azabi qaynamoq; birovning adabini berib qo'yimoq.

Quyida ingliz hamda rus tillarida ham ijobiy ham salbiy kontekstlarda qo'llaniladigan insonni turli hissiyotlar va emotsional holatini bildiruvchi tilde eng ko'p uchraydigan frazeologik birliklarni taqdim etamiz: On cloud nine - extremely happy. I'm on cloud nine.

Like a dog with two tails - used to emphasize how delighted someone is. He's like a dog with two tails down there.

Full of the joys of spring - be lively and cheerful. Someone's full of the joys of spring!

Over the moon - extremely happy; delighted. And I was over the moon.

On top of the world - happy and elated.

Feel blue - feel sad. He knows just how to make me laugh when I feel blue.

Down in the dumps - (of a person) depressed or unhappy. No wonder you're down in the dumps.

At my wit's end - to be so worried, confused, or annoyed that you do not know what to do next. I'm at my wit's end. I can't cope.

It makes my blood boil! - something makes somebody extremely angry. It's the drawing-room school of Shakespeare. Makes my blood boil.

I'm fed up with it! - to be tired of something. I'm fed up with that dance and I'm cold.

Butterflies in my stomach - you are anxious and have a nervous feeling in your stomach. And I got those little butterflies in my stomach like I was 17 again.

Goosebumps - a state of the skin caused by cold, fear, or excitement, in which small bumps appear on the surface as the hairs become erect; goose pimples. I got goosebumps all over, look...

On pins and needles - in an agitated state of suspense. The polls back east close in less than an hour and we're all just on pins and needles.

Spaced out - euphoric, disoriented, or unaware of one's surroundings. I saw you standing there all spaced out.

Shaken up - If you are shaken up by an unpleasant experience, or if something shakes you up, it makes you feel shocked and upset, and unable to think calmly or clearly. She's fine, just a little shaken up.

Bushed - tired out; exhausted. I'm back from work, I'm bushed.

Head over heels - madly in love. I'm head over heels in love with you.

Under the weather - slightly unwell or in low spirits. Is she still under the weather?

Yuqorida ingliz tilida keltirilgan frazeologik birliklardan iborat bo'lgan misollarda biz insonning turli emotsional holatini his qilishimiz mumkin.

Rus tili ham turli insonning emotsional holatini ifodalovchi frazeologik birliklarga boy hisoblanadi. Quyida rus tilida emotsional holatni bildiruvchi iboralardan misollar keltiramiz: "в наимрачнейшем расположении духа" - juda ham yomon, tushkun emotsional holatda bo'lmoq, "в истерике (какой-либо) (в какой-либо) истерике" - vahimali holatda bo'lmoq, в (каком-либо) изумлении (в изумлении (каком-либо) - qandaydir hayratli holatda bo'lmoq, в (каком-либо) замешательстве (в замешательстве (каком-либо) - nima qilishini bilmaslik, ikkilanmoq, в душе пустынная пустыня - chuqur qayg'uda bo'lmoq, tushkunlikga tushgan, nima qilishini bilmaslik, yakka, в (какой-либо) гармонии (в гармонии (какой-либо) - ichki olami tinch, хотирjam, бледный (-ая, -ые) как смерть (как смерть бледный) - nima qilishini bilmaydi, murakkab holatga tushib qolgan, qo'rqib qolgan, белый (-ая; -ые) от ярости (от ярости белый, -ая; -ые) - jahli chiqqan, g'azab otiga mingan, g'azabli, без (какого-либо) трепета (без трепета (какого-либо) - hech qanday ortiqcha harakatsiz, har qanday ortiqcha harakatsiz, без (какой-либо) грусти (без грусти (какой-либо) - xafagarchiliksiz, без (каких-либо) улыбок (без улыбок (каких-либо) - xafa, g'amgin.

Frazeologiya sohasi hozirgi kunga kelib ancha keng qamrovda tushunilmoqda, ya'ni nafaqat turg'un so'z birliklar balki maqol va matallar, naql va latifalar ham shu sohaga oid deb qaralmoqda. Xalqning rasm-rusumlari, urf - odatlari, turmush qiyinchiliklari, mehnat-majburiyatlari, xursandchiliklari, hayot tarzi ushbu birliklarda o'z aksini topadi va tabiiyki bir tildan ikkinchi bir tilga bu birliklarni tarjima qilishda ancha qiyinchiliklar yuzaga keladi. Ma'lumki, ingliz va rus tillari tarixan ikki xil turli madaniyatga mansubdir va bu ikki tilning turli xil madaniyat va urf- odatlarga ega ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Va ingliz tilidagi mavjud frazeologik birliklarni rus tiliga tarjima qilishda va muqobil variantini topishda ayrim muammolar keltirib chiqaradi. Quyida mana shu iboralarni o'ziga xos jihatlarini ko'rib chiqamiz: "over the moon" idiomasi so'zma -so'z tarjima qilinsa "oydan baland bo'lmoq" degan ma'noni beradi lekin uni rus tilidagi muqobil varianti "быть на седьмом небе" degan ma'noga mos tushadi. Keltirilgan misolda frazeologik birlikni o'zak komponentlari ma'nosidan anglashib bo'lmaydi va bu ko'chma ma'noda ishlatiladi. Boshqa misolni kuzatsak: "Break smb's heart", bu birlik rus tilidagi "разбить сердце" degan muqobil variantlarga egadir. Ba'zan turlicha oilaga mansub bo'lgan turli tillarda shaklan turlicha bo'lsada obrazli asoslari o'xshash mazmun jihatdan bir biriga yaqin frazeologik birliklar uchrashi qadim zamonlardan xalqlar o'rtasida davom etib kelayotgan do'stlik va qardoshlik aloqalaridan darak beradi. Masalan: "To be on the high horse" - ingliz tilida "baland otda bo'lmoq" deb tushunilsa, o'zbekchada esa "burni ko'tarilmoq", rus tilida esa "быть на коне" degan ekvivalentga mos tushadi. Bular ikkala tilda turlicha jaranglasada baribir, mazmunan man-mansirab ketmoq degan ma'noni anglatadi. Yoki "to be two faced" birikmasi inglizchadan so'zma so'z "ikki yuzli bo'lmoq" deb tarjima qilinadi va o'zbek tilidagi "ikki yuzlamachi" degan ekvivalentiga egadir, rus tilida ham deyarli shu shakldagi ibora mavjud: двуличной.

Insonning quvnoqligini, xursandligini bildiradigan iboralardan misollar keltirishda davom etamiz: To leap/jump for joy, shunday xursand bo'lishki, sakrab yuborishga oz qoladi. Masalan: "She couldn't help but leap for joy when they offered her the job." Mazkur quvnoqlik ottenkasiga ega psixoemotsional holatni anglatuvchi iboraga ekvivalent qilib, rus tilida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan iboralardan birini keltirishimiz mumkin "на седьмом небе от счастья". Xursandchilik kontekstida ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan bir nechta iboralarni ikkala tilda ham keltirib o'tdik, faqat ularning ichida ma'no jihatdan kuchlilari eng so'nggi birliklar hisoblanadi.

To burst with joy iborasi ham xursandchilikdan oshib toshmoq degan ma'noda qo'llaniladi, (to feel full to a figurative point of bursting with happiness). Ex. "My daughter was bursting with joy while getting ready for her first day of school." To weep for joy, means to cry out of pure happiness. Ex. "It was hard not to weep for joy when I saw my brother." Mazkur ibora ham quvnoqlik sinonimik qatorda ishlatiladigan iboralarda ishlatiladigan frazeologik birliklardan biri hisoblanadi. To be on cloud nine frazeologik birligi esa "xursandligidan osmonlarda uchmoq" yoki rus tilidagi o'zining ekvivalentiga ham ega deb aytish mumkin, "на девятом небе" frazeologik birligi ham xuddi ingliz tilidagidek "osmon" leksik birligini o'z ichiga olgan, bu yerda ham tillardagi insonning emotsional holatini ifodalashda xizmat qiladigan iboraning shaklan va ma'no jihatdan shakllanishi bir-biriga ancha yaqin ekanligiga amin bo'lmoqdamiz. To be on cloud nine means to be overwhelmed with happiness, satisfaction, or excitement. Ex. "Rachel felt like she was on cloud nine when she finally bought her dream house."

Ko'rib turganingizdek, yuqoridagi barcha idiomalar quvonch va baxtni anglatadi. Endi biz g'azab va umidsizlikni tasvirlaydigan idiomalarga e'tibor qaratamiz. Ba'zida xotirjamlikni saqlash qiyin bo'lishi mumkin. Bunday paytlarda biz asabiylashish, umidsizlik yoki boshqa salbiy his-tuyg'ularni boshdan kechirishimiz mumkin. Bu idiomalar qayg'uli, xafa va shunga o'xshash salbiy ottenkali psixoemotsional holatni bildiradi hamda ularni idiomalar bilan tasvirlashda yordam beradi:

To get under one's skin, means to annoy someone through behavior or communication. Ex. "As much as she tried, her teenager daughter's behavior got under Elaine's skin." Biror kishining teri ostiga tushish, hatti-harakatlar yoki muloqot orqali kimnidir bezovta qilish, joniga tegishni anglatadigan ibora ingliz tilida ancha uzoq vaqtdan beri ishlatiladigan frazeologik birliklardan biri hisoblanadi. Ingliz tilida insonning psixoemotsional holatini bildiradigan yana bir frazeologizm bu "to push one's buttons" hisoblanadi, uning ingliz tilidagi ma'nosi "to cause a strong reaction or emotional response in someone; to provoke a negative response" dir. Ushbu ibora o'zbek tilida "biror bir kishida kuchli reaksiya yoki emotsional javobni berishga majbur qilish, salbiy ma'nodagi javob berishga sababchi bo'lish" degan ma'nolarga ega, mazkur frazeologik birlikning rus tilida ekvivalenti yo'q. Ex. "My brother knew exactly how to push my buttons and get me in trouble with our parents." Keyingi salbiy ottenkali frazeologik birligimiz bu "to be on edge" hisoblanadi, "to be nervous, anxious, irritated, and/or unrelaxed".

Frazeologik birliklarning lingvokognitiv tahlili ularning etimologik kelib chiqishi haqida ham ma'lum bir ma'lumotlarni tilshunoslarga taqdim eta oladi, har bir iboraning salbiy yoki ijobiy ottenka olishiga ma'lum bir voqea hodisalar sababchi bo'ladi, jumladan, "avzo" so'zi "yuz" sinonimik qatordagi eng salbiy ma'noli birlik sanaladi, buning salbiylik xususiyati iboraga ham ko'chgan. "To lose one's temper/to lose it", means to lose composure and visibly show anger. Yuqoridagi ibora "toqati toq bo'lmoq", "sabr kosasi to'lmoq" kabi iboralar bilan ekvivalentlik holatlarini hosil qiladi. Ex. "My mom lost it when she found out that I had failed my test." To get triggered, means to experience or have an emotional reaction to a disturbing topic in the media or social setting or to something that is associated with the memory of a past, negative event. Mazkur ibora ingliz tilida eng ko'p og'zaki nutqda qo'llaniladigan frazeologizmlardan biri hisoblanadi, uning o'zbek tilidagi ekvivalenti yo'q, ma'nosi esa "salbiy, yomonroq xotiralarni esga solmoq" hisoblanadi. Ex. "Watching the movie triggered me and I couldn't finish the rest." To lash out, means to suddenly attack someone, verbally or physically, from a point of anger. Mazkur ibora insonning juda ham kuchli emotsional holatda bo'lib, boshqalarga to'satdan tashlanmoq degan ma'noga ega, u o'zbek tilidagi "g'azab otiga minmoq" frazeologizmiga mos keladi. Ex. "She lashed out when she found out she lost her job." Quyidagi frazeologik birliklar ham birdaniga, kutilmaganda, to'satdan vajohatga kirib, kishilarga tashlanish holatini bildiradi: "to blow a fuse", means to become extremely angry. Ex. "Jamie's aunt blew a fuse when she found out that we weren't coming over for Thanksgiving this year." "To go ballistic", means to become extremely angry and fly into a blind rage. Ex. "Fans went ballistic when they found out that their favorite singer was cut from the show." "To flip a lid", means to become angry in a crazy, uncontrolled manner. Ex. "My supervisor will flip his lid again if we don't meet today's target." Rus tilida ham mana shunday kuchli salbiy emotsional holatlarni ifodalaydigan bir nechta iboralar mavjud, shulardan biri "снесло крышу" – bir lahzaning o'zida nihoyatda g'azablandi; g'azab otiga mindi – qattiq jahli chiqdi va boshqalar.

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